

ADAPTIVE EDUCATIONAL APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF EUROPEAN (CIS) COUNTRIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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ANNOTATION

Institutional changes in higher education are taking place at a very fast pace. The reform is being implemented in a very short period of time. As universities grow in size and become more expensive for the state, administrative pressure increases, and the number of control procedures and regulatory mechanisms increases. At the same time, the atmosphere in higher education institutions is becoming tense and uncertainty is increasing. Therefore, teachers and students involved in the educational process must adapt to the ever-changing and increasingly complex rules. Institutional economic theory and qualitative analysis methods served as the conceptual basis of the research on identifying and explaining adaptation mechanisms in higher education. In the article, we study and reflect on the use of adaptive education in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan today, as well as the experiences of the CIS countries.

Keywords: *adaptive behavior, adaptive changes, Higher education, government reforms, Uzbekistan, qualitative research, educational system, educational process.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Институциональные изменения в высшем образовании происходят очень быстрыми темпами. Реформа реализуется в очень сжатые сроки. По мере

того, как университеты растут в размерах и становятся дороже для государства, увеличивается административное давление, увеличивается количество контрольных процедур и механизмов регулирования. В то же время атмосфера в высших учебных заведениях становится напряженной и неопределенность возрастает. Поэтому учителя и студенты, участвующие в образовательном процессе, должны адаптироваться к постоянно меняющимся и усложняющимся правилам. Институциональная экономическая теория и методы качественного анализа послужили концептуальной основой исследований по выявлению и объяснению механизмов адаптации в высшем образовании. В статье мы изучаем и размышляем над использованием адаптивного образования в высших учебных заведениях Узбекистана сегодня, а также опыт стран СНГ.

Ключевые слова: *адаптивное поведение, адаптивные изменения, высшее образование, государственные реформы, Узбекистан, качественные исследования, образовательная система, образовательный процесс.*

INTRODUCTION

Since the 60s of the twentieth century, some organizations began to face rapid changes in the external environment, so many of them developed and implemented new, flexible types of organizational structures that are better than traditional (vertical) structures. began to reach. adapted to the rapid changes in the external environment. conditions and the emergence of science-demanding and innovative technologies. Such structures are called adaptive, because they can be quickly changed in accordance with changes in the environment and the needs of the organization itself. Adaptation is the process of forming a structure to suit a particular environment. Successful adaptation leads to organizational survival. Adaptation of higher education institutions occurs due to state regulation through material, financial and personnel resources, market pressure, modern information technologies and legal documents.

METHODS

Ongoing research claims to partially fill the research gap, which is actually an attempt to implement institutional monitoring - monitoring the order and effectiveness of reforms implemented in the field of education in Uzbekistan. The theoretical and methodological framework of the study was formed by traditional institutionalism based on pragmatist philosophical foundations (see also: Stanfield, 1999; Gruchy, 1947; Mirowski, 1987; Hodgson, 2000; Parada, 2006; Dewey, et al.) - practical interdisciplinary approach to the studied problem, covering economic, legal and ethical aspects of economic behavior. The qualitative methodology used in the study suggests that any socio-economic phenomenon should be studied in the context of the accompanying norms (Commons, 2012) that have meaning in a particular society. Thus, the sample for the study is 50 representatives of three communities in the field of higher education: the heads of structural units of universities (including representatives of administrative staff, some of whom are not currently teachers), teachers and students was formed. The choice of qualitative research methodology is justified by relying on traditional institutionalism (see also: Rutherford, 2011; 2012; Commons, 1998; 2012; Efimov, 2016). The practical importance of this methodology is that issues related to the development of socio-economic policies must inevitably include the identification of the relevant beliefs of the main subjects directly affected by the changes resulting from this policy. These beliefs form the basis of customs (e.g. Hodgson, 2000; Dequech, 2013) and reflect whether or not there is agreement among members of certain communities on certain policies implemented by authorities. Thus, an important part of the institutional analysis becomes to explain the actual prospects of the policy being carried out, in particular, the possibility of its acceptance or rejection by the population, in other words, what will be the new rules and orders transmitted through the policy? remains only an officially announced, non-institutionalized rule (see also Efimov, 2016), which inevitably raises issues of "careful institutional design" of socio-economic policies (see, e.g., Hodgson, 2013).

Aspects covered by institutional analysis are economics, law and ethics (Commons, 2012; Chavance, 2012).

RESULTS

If we build a model with actors who act rationally, how will the education sector of Uzbekistan develop? Most likely, it represents a semi-desert, which alone has been swept away by the sands of oblivion of elite metropolitan research universities and provincial universities. Why does this happen, according to the hypothesis of rational behavior? And why not really? We try to answer these questions using the methods of interpretive institutionalism and the concept of adaptive rationality. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, work in higher education institutions gradually began to lose its prestige. For 25 years, teacher salaries have rarely reached the average level for a given region. Of course, teachers' investment in human capital is unique, which may explain, for example, their attempts to keep (at least partially) their university jobs. But the lack of clear financial prospects for professors for a long time forces us to look for alternative explanations for continuing to work in universities. One such explanation can be the hypothesis of an increase in hidden income in the field of higher education in the 90s and zeros (Klyamkin, Timofeev, 2000). It is no coincidence that in those years well-structured markets for students' final qualification works, dissertations and other shadow services appeared, which made it possible to purchase the necessary diplomas and scientific degrees. Perhaps this adaptation was the only possible form of survival for a significant part of the university community. In the last 10 years, significant changes have taken place in Uzbekistan, affecting both the quality and quantity indicators of the higher education system. These changes have a significant impact on the decision-making process of the participants of the educational services market, as well as shape their further behavior. To study the adaptive behavior of participants in the organization of the educational process, we consider the impact of the most important changes for teachers and students, which determines their further behavior, and also based on the concept of adaptive rationality, we define the types of these behaviors. The analysis

of 20 in-depth interviews conducted with teachers of the city of Tashkent in 2020 showed that the biggest impact on the educational process is related to the bureaucratization of the educational process and the increase in the administrative burden. According to the respondents, this has a negative impact on the educational process: "Every month, a bunch of unnecessary reports add nervousness to the teaching process"; "Lectures take a lot of time due to preparation for lectures." In the second place of importance, teachers emphasize the transition to a two-level system of "bachelor and master". This change has a twofold effect on the educational process. On the one hand, the classroom hours are decreasing, the hours for independent work of students are increasing, and the amount of courses necessary for successful mastery of the subject at the undergraduate level should be reduced. On the other hand, in the master's degree, students can engage more deeply in scientific activities and improve their professional skills.

DISCUSSION

As a form of adaptive behavior, obedience may represent a hidden form of opportunism, which, due to the changed institutional environment and economic conditions, was prone to symbiosis with obedience. For example, a teacher in his behavior may show complete obedience in fulfilling some obligations, but at the same time, his motivation decreases in fulfilling others: "I want to be creative in the process of organizing educational activities." I will stop. Now we are given orders and decrees, and as a conscientious, law-abiding officer, I must carry them out. I am not paid for discussing orders, but for carrying them out."

CONCLUSION

The social significance and uniqueness of the organizational culture in our higher educational institutions is related to the social values and institutions formed in an evolutionary way. However, in the course of reforms, not all participants understand and correctly interpret regulatory measures and management decisions, which is also a negative factor in the formation of effective (allowing to carry out transactions at a lower cost and increasing the regularity of transactions) existing

rules. Thus, it is reasonable to doubt the correctness of the institutional reforms carried out in the higher education system of our country in recent years, which are trying to fully transfer to a market-oriented system and in practice, along with the introduction of legislation. It is not enough. Reforms "from above". Compulsory organization of public discussions involving representatives of the communities that make up the educational system in the reform process is a necessary condition for saving higher education. At the same time, systematic qualitative research focusing on the perceptions of educational subjects about the institutional changes being implemented is a tool for better understanding not only "what" but "how it should be" - how inevitable and important the reforms should be. It must be developed and implemented in accordance with the modernization of the economy and society and the requirements of the time.

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